

INFLUENCE OF ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD WITH FREQUENCY 300 Hz ON MARINE MICROBIOTA

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At the base of Institute of Natural and Technical Systems (INTS), studies of the influence of the electromagnetic field (EMF) on the Black Sea microbiota were continued. Our first experiments showed that the effect of electromagnetic load on marine microbiota leads to a decrease in the infectious titer in algal viruses and an increase in resistance (decrease in sensitivity) to viral lysis in microalgae by 1–2 orders of magnitude (Stepanova et al. 2023).

The purpose (goal) of continued research was the study the effect of EMF with a maximum frequency of 300 Hz and a signal level of 120-150 mV on marine microbiota.

The experiments were carried out using a laboratory installation developed at the Laboratory of Hydrophysical and Bioelectronic Measurement Systems and Technologies of the Center for Environmental Engineering and Sustainable Energy INTS (LHBMST CEISE INTS) (Penkov et al., 2022), which, after improvement, made it possible to create EMF with a maximum frequency of 300 Hz and a level signal 120–150 mV.

The studied marine microbiota was used as viral suspensions of the algal virus TvV (strain TvV-SI-1) with different infectious titers and viral host – a culture of the microalgae *Tetraselmis viridis*. The methodology for setting up experiments and recording the results were described in detail earlier (Penkov et al. 2022; Stepanova et al., 2023).

A total of 12 experiments were carried out, of which 6 were on EMF irradiation of a liquid culture of the microalgae *Tetraselmis viridis* and 6 on the effect of EMF on the viral suspension of the TvV-SI-1 strain. The results for the first time recorded an increase in the infectious titer of the used algal virus strain TvV by 1-4 orders of magnitude after exposure to an EMF with specified characteristics (300 Hz and 120-150 mV). In the microalgae *Tetraselmis viridis*, in 4 experiments, no differences were noted between the irradiated (experimental) culture and the control sample in sensitivity to viral lysis; in 2 cases a decrease in resistance by 2 orders of magnitude was observed.

According to our assumption, the fact of an increase in the infectious titer of the algal virus of microalgae *Tetraselmis viridis* (strain TvV-SI-1) recorded in experiments after exposure to EMF with a high frequency (300 Hz) and an enhanced signal level may be associated with a sharp decrease in adhesion properties (gluing, gluing, adhesion) in viral particles. This can lead to an increase in the concentration of viruses in the suspension and leveling out the usually inhibitory (oppression) effect of the electromagnetic load.

Research in this direction will be continued to further study the effect of the electromagnetic field on marine microbiota.

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References:

Stepanova O.A., Sholar S.A., Penkov M.N. Results of studying the influence of the electromagnetic field on marine microbiota // Environmental Control Systems. 2023. No. 2 (52). pp. 32–39.

Penkov M.N., Sholar S.A., Stepanova O.A. Laboratory installation for studying the influence of an alternating electromagnetic field on marine microbiota // Environmental Control Systems. 2022. No. 3 (49). pp. 37–43.